

Efficient hardware implementation for lightweight Loong algorithm using FPGA

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ABSTRACT

Recently low-resource devices such as radio frequency identification (RFID), internet of things (IoT), and wireless sensor networks (WSN) using lightweight cryptography (LWC) to protect devices. Created or design low-resource devices with a lightweight cryptographic technique should take into account important factors such as the battery life and the amount of data to be processed. This paper provides a new hardware designed for Loong lightweight cryptographic algorithm that takes into account the previously described constraints. The new hardware architecture for Loong algorithm with resource sharing to reduce system designed. The proposed approach is implemented using ISE Xilinx V14.7 using Virtex 4 field programmable gate array (FPGA) platform. The synthesis analysis for ISE showed the throughput of 851.264 Mbps with efficiency of 2.282 Mbps/slice, and a power consumption of 0.193 Watt. The implementation designed show the all-algorithms size consists of 373 slices, and the maximum possible operating frequency is 212.816 MHz. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that Loong algorithm has been implemented on FPGA using very high-speed integrated circuit hardware description language (VHDL).

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1. INTRODUCTION

Computer networks play an important role in our daily lives. Used by various applications such as the world wide web (WWW), electronic messaging or the transfer of computer files, they allow us to acquire information as well as to communicate and exchange data permanently. It is now possible to connect any object of our daily life to a network, and we speak of Internet of things to designate all of these connected objects. The internet of things (IoT) has many application areas and thus offers immense potential for companies [1], industries and users. The lightweight cryptography algorithms used for develop many applications like electronic clinical record prototype that designed to work with low-performance devices. These electronic clinical record seek to secure the information without losing optimal performance and ensure low computational consumption [2].

The block cipher is one of important types of lightweight cryptography algorithm, such as RoadRunner [3], shadow [4], KLEIN [5], AES [6], GOST [7], LBlock [8], SFN [9], Midori [10], TWINE [11], and SPARX [12], which provide us with smaller block sizes than conventional lightweight cryptography (LWC), most key sizes ranging from 80 bits to 112-bit keys according to what was established in the National Institute Standards Technology (NIST), simpler rounds with an 8-bit S-box preference and programming simpler keys that generate sub-keys that increase of memory, latency, and power consumption [13]. Tools have

very limited resources, memory, power consumption, and processing speed capacities. Because of these limitations, traditional encryption cannot be used on devices with low storage space. As a direct result, the concept of "lightweight cryptography" was considered. As a result of the rapid development of new technologies gaining popularity, an entirely new form of encryption known as "lightweight" has been created. Due to the complexity of the computational operations required in traditional cryptography. The goal of lightweight cryptography is to reduce hardware-oriented and software-oriented implementation costs. Lightweight cryptography refers to an encryption technology designed for use in rapidly expanding applications that rely heavily on technology with limited resources [14].

In this paper, we analyze the security issues of connected objects, linked on the one hand to the large amount of data they handle, and on the other to the fact that they are often in a hostile environment and physically accessible. Then new hardware architecture implemented using field-programmable gate array (FPGA) platforms for Loong lightweight block cipher algorithms. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: section 2 we will explain the concept of lightweight block cipher algorithms, in section 3 we will review some of the LWC concepts, in section 4 we will present our model for LWC based on FPGA, and finally we will conclude our work in section 5. Recently many lightweight block cipher algorithms are implemented using FPGA board for IoT application. Many of lightweight block ciphers have been proposed e.g. PRINCE [15], LED [16], mCrypton [17], and PRESENT [18]. All of these ciphers are designed and aimed at specifically for extremely constrained environments such as radio frequency identification (RFID) tags and sensor networks. Abbas *et al.* [15] the authors design new FPGA IP-core which is to speed-up the performance of PRINCE. LED is a symmetric block cipher whose block size is 64 bits and its internal architecture is based on the substitution-permutation network (SPN). It is designed in two versions based on the key size; 64-bit key (LED-64) and 128-bit key (LED-128). Its number of rounds is based on the size of the encryption key; LED-64 has 32 rounds while LED-128 has 48 rounds [16]. The mCrypton algorithm is a 64-bit lightweight block cipher cryptographic algorithm. Substitution permutation (SP) structure is used in design of mCrypton algorithm architecture [17]. A set of existing optimized lightweight cryptographic architectures are discussed here. Singh *et al.* [8] for LBlock is a 64-bit block cipher with an 80-bit key and 32 rounds. Mhaouch *et al.* [18] for the present the cipher is based on a substitution-permutation network (SPN). Present supports 64-bit input data blocks and key sizes of 80 and 128 bits. In [19] LILLIPUT cipher transforms 64-bits of plaintext into 64-bits of cipher text with 80-bits of the key. Anusha and Shastrimath [20] introduced XTEA which includes 64-bit block size (Plain text) and 128-bit key size. Zeebaree [21] for DES, data are encrypted in 64-bit blocks using a 56-bit key. So that the comparison would be as precise as possible, they used the same security level, technology, and hardware/software implementation complexity factors (chip area, throughput, latency, and power consumption) for each of the block ciphers under consideration [22], [23].

2. METHOD

2.1. Loong algorithm

SPN-based Loong includes a 128-bit key block addition to the 64-bit key. The values of 16, 20, and 32 according to the round number (RN) system. The length of each of the three keys is what determines which of the three algorithms Loong-64, Loong-80, and Loong-128 is applied to the encryption process. Because Loong was the first algorithm to develop the round function technique, we are able to write "SubCells!" and "MixRows!" AddRoundKey. This symmetrical and lightweight block cipher has been given the name Loong. It gets its name from the fact that its round function uses two different SubCells algorithms. AddRoundKey, Sub-Cells, MixRows, and MixColumns are some of the sub-functions that are available to you when you use the round function [24]. A number of round features, including AddRoundKey, SubCells, MixRows, and MixColumns, are available in Figure 1.

It is common knowledge that the AES technique utilizes the SPN structure as its foundation. In contrast to the Feistel network structure, the SPN network structure is able to produce round functions despite having a greater degree of confusion and diffusion than the latter. In comparison to other forms of computer programming, SPN-based algorithms offer superior levels of both productivity and dependability. In contrast, the process of encrypting and decrypting data is approached in a different manner by algorithms that are based on SPN [25]. In order to solve this problem, we propose that the SPN adopt a new organizational structure. In this newly designed SPN architecture, the operations of encrypting information with a cipher and decrypting it are exactly the same, Thus the Loong structure is highly efficient and secure.

As a direct consequence of this, the SPN structure used by the Loong has been entirely rethought and revised. SubCells (SC), MixRows (MR), MixColumns (MC), and AddRoundKey (AR) are the four round transformations that make up Loong's round transformations (ARK) as show in Figure 2. To best characterize these constituents, the word "involutionary" is the one that works best [24]. The example that follows is an illustration of the round function used in Loong's encryption.

$$\left(\begin{matrix} ENC_{RN}[RC^0, \dots, RC^{RN}] = ARK(RK, RC^0) \\ o(\bigcirc_{r=1}^{RN} SC \circ MR \circ MC \circ SC \circ ARK(RK, RC^{RN})) \end{matrix} \right) [24] \tag{1}$$

As a result, the encryption and decryption of Loong are identical. Decryption uses round constants in the opposite order as encryption. We are required to give evidence that the encryption and decryption technologies are equivalent [24].

Figure 1. Process function of Loong algorithm [24]

Figure 2. Diffusion effect in Loong [24]

2.1.1. Encryption process using Loong algorithm

SPN-based A 64-bit block in Loong is equivalent to a 64-bit round number, while an 80-bit key block is equivalent to a 64-bit round number, and a 128-bit key block is equivalent to a 128-bit round number (RN). The length of the three keys is used to determine which of the three Loong designations an algorithm is given: Loong-64, Loong-80, or Loong-128 [24]. The fundamental difference between Loong's encryption and decryption techniques is that the former uses round constants in the opposite sequence of the latter. This is the case while encrypting data. A number of round features, including AddRoundKey, SubCells, MixRows, and MixColumns, are available in Loong as shown in Figure 3. Provides an explanation of the intricate encryption process that Loong employed [24].

The method of enciphering data with the Loong cipher can also be referred to as ENC_{RN} . Plaintext is what ENC_{RN} takes in as its input, and the plaintext itself can be segmented into multiple 64-bit plaintext blocks in addition to a primary key if necessary. The encryption procedures for Loong-64, Loong-80, and Loong-128 are each represented by ENC_{16} , ENC_{20} , and ENC_{32} , respectively [24].

$$ENC_{RN} : \begin{cases} \{0,1\}^{64} \times \{0,1\}^{K_{RN}} \rightarrow \{0,1\}^{64} \\ (plaintext, key) \rightarrow ciphertext \end{cases} [24] \tag{2}$$

In this particular instance, RN is equal to 16, 20, and 32, and the total value of K16, K20, and K32 is equal to 64. In Algorithm 1, the ENC_{RN} is illustrated by making use of a 64-bit Round Key (RK), which is a topic that is covered in key scheduling.

Algorithm 1. Loong routine

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 $ENC_{RN}$ 
Input: Plaintext, RK, RC;
Output: Ciphertext;
1: state ← Plaintext;
2: AddRoundKey (state, RK, RC);
3: for i=1 to RN do
4: SubCells (state);
5: MixRows (state);
6: MixColumns (state);
7: SubCells (state);
8: AddRoundKey (state, RK, RC);
    
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9: endfor
10: Ciphertext ← state;
11: Return Ciphertext;
    
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2.1.2. Decryption process

This approach, which is the same process as the Loong cipher's inverse, is used to construct both the Loong cipher and its inverse. The process of encrypting and decrypting data follows the same pattern when it comes to the flow of the data. Long messages can be decrypted if the round constants are read backwards from the sequence in which they were written [24]. This method is known as "reverse reading." This Loong decryption is very quick and user-friendly as a direct result of this, thanks to the fact that it uses a direct consequence see Figure 4.

Figure 3. Encryption Loong algorithm

Figure 4. Decryption Loong algorithm

2.2. FPGA implementation

The field-programmable gate array, also known as an FPGA, is used to implement the lightweight block cipher encryption and hash function in hardware [25]. The hardware designed with different architectures. Also the architecture that is based on iterative looping has as its primary goal the reduction in the total number of hardware resources that are required for the design [26]. As a consequence of this, the design of loop unrolling no longer necessitates a number of round transformations equal to the algorithm's round count; rather, it only necessitates a single round transformation and the associated registers [27], [28]. This change was brought about as a result of the fact that loop unrolling no longer requires a number of round transformations equal to the algorithm's round count. Because of this, it is suitable for use in applications that are on a more limited scale [29]. The clock will be allowed to completely revolve around its axis once for each round of the competition. In order for this design to work as intended, the flow of operations needs to be controlled by a block of control logic as well [30], [31]. An FPGA is made up of a matrix of programmable logic units that may be reconfigured complex logic blocks (CLBs). The development of digital systems makes considerable use of FPGAs [18]. An FPGA is made up of a matrix of programmable logic units that may be reconfigured. Loop unrolling no longer requires a number of round transformations equal to the algorithm's round count. Because of this, it is suitable for use in applications that are on a more limited scale. The very

high-speed integrated circuit hardware description language (VHDL) language is used to implement the LWC Loong algorithm. Figure 5 shows the RTL top module for our proposal system. The proposal designed consist from four input ports and only one output port. The proposal designed base on FPGA Virtex 4 platforms.

Figure 5. Top module of Loong RTL

3. THE LOONG HARDWARE COMPONENT

Loong is a lightweight block cipher algorithm that supports a block length of 64 bits with a key size of (64/80/128) bits. It consists of AddRoundKey, SubCells, MixRows, MixColumns, SubCells and AddRoundKey. The Loong algorithm decryption unit is about similar to the encryption design but the only variance between the encryption and the decryption is using round-constants in inverse order.

3.1. Subcell

The hardware implementation of 64-bit S-Box is presented in Figure 6. The input/ouput of S-Box component is 64-bit contains sixteen subcell (Sbox) with 4-bit input/output. The D Flip Flop are used to implemented the Subcell to reduce the hardware footprint.

Figure 6. RTL of Subcell

3.2. MixRo

The hardware implementation of 64-bit MixRow is presented in Figure 7. The encryption process is used sixteen Multiplexers. Each Multiplexer used 4-bit input and 1-bit output.

Figure 7. RTL of MixRow

3.3. MixColumn

Figure 8 show RTL of 64-bit MixColumn. The encryption process is used sixteen Multipliers. Each Multiplier is used 4-bit input and 1-bit output.

Figure 8. RTL of MixColumn

3.4. AddRoundkey

The last component show in the Figure 9 described the implementation of Add round key that used two time every round. The input/output is 64-bit, first time the plaintext XOR with round key. Second time with every round the output from Mix column component is XOR with round key (RK) and the round constants (RC).

Figure 9. RTL of AddRoundKey

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main target of this paper is implement small hardware design for Loong algorithm with low of latency. The amount of data that is transferred during permutation designed using wire only as well as row-to-column conversion. The new architecture designed and implemented using ISE, then ISim simulation program was used to execute the Loong algorithm with test vectors. The plaintext and key size is 64-bit. Figure 10 shows the outputs of the simulation that was run on the most current three system components that were constructed, as well as the results of the most recent data that was input into the design. A relatively low number of slices is required in order for the proposed architecture to function properly and successfully meet the goals of high frequency and high throughput. When working in shift mode, it is possible to reduce the total number of slices by making use of the lookup table (LUT) technique. The LUT is responsible for transferring data by shuffling the order of the input and output data places. The shift operation that makes use of LUTs can be carried out in a single cycle of the clock if necessary. As show in Figure 11 show the decryption process.

When utilizing this design, it is necessary to utilize a total of sixteen clock cycles in order to process the inputs and produce the cipher text. The results of running the simulation on the remaining three parts of the system that is being envisioned along with the last round of data input. It has been proved that the proposed pipeline architecture is effective even with a constrained number of slices when it comes to the execution of tasks that need high frequency and high throughput. During shift operations, the number of slices may be cut down to a more manageable level thanks to the LUT technique. A LUT will shift both the input data values and the output data values whenever it is given the instruction to perform a shift operation. It is possible for the shift operation that makes use of LUTs to be finished in a single cycle of the clock. Reducing the number of slices used in the creation of a design for RFID or IoT applications. Area is defined as the total number of

slices. The results of the design architecture performance are displayed in Table 1. These results have a high throughput with small area and small energy. In addition, the implementation for proposal design show throughput 851.264 Mbps, efficiency of 2.28 Mbps per slice, and total power consumption of 0.193 mW.

Figure 10. Simulation of Loong encryption

Figure 11. Simulation of Loong decryption

Table 1. Compares the encryption and decryption resources given by Loong to those provide

Algorithm	Block size	FPGA Device	Max. Freq. (MHz)	Throughput (Mbps)	Total Slices	Efficiency	Power (mWatt)
Proposed Loong	64	Virtex-4	212.816	851.264	373	2.282	0.193
LBLOCK [8]	64	Virtex-4	315.00	635.021	158	4.02	0.878
PRESENT [21]	64	Virtex-4	364.56	171.56	152	0.041	248.02
LILLIPUT [22]	64	Virtex-4	654.24	465.24	3313	-----	285.00
TEA [23]	64	Artix-7	263.762	80.43	238	0.34	0.222

5. CONCLUSION

Efficient hardware architecture for the Loong lightweight encryption algorithm is designed and implemented in this paper. The area and power are optimized for our new architecture based on FPGAs. The utilization of a resource structure that is shared by using multiple component to process algorithms. All component is designed to execute through sixteen clock cycles. The results for implement Loong algorithm using Xilinx Virtex-4 FPGA show that number of slices is 373 with an operating frequency 212.816 MHz and a power consumption of 0.192 mWatt. In addition, a total throughput of 851.264 Mbps with a slice efficiency of 2.282 Mbps/slice. Finally the result of hardware proposal designed for LWC Loong algorithm shows that it is appropriate for mobile and small devices.

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